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Pathogenetic Mechanisms of Endothelial Dysfunction in Retinopathy in Patients with Arterial Hypertension

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***Abstract:** To assess vascular wall stiffness and endothelial function in patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM) with and without different stages of diabetic nephropathy (DN).*

Materials and methods.

A total of 93 patients with type 1 diabetes, aged 18 to 40 years, with a disease duration of more than 5 years, were examined. The criterion for forming groups was the stage of DN. The control group consisted of 23 healthy people. The study included evaluation of pulse wave contour analysis and reactive hyperemia test using the Angioscan device.

Results.

When conducting pulse wave contour analysis, the aortic stiffness index was significantly higher in all groups of patients with DN compared with healthy subjects. However, when comparing patients with type 1 diabetes without DN with the control group, no significant differences were found in the stiffness index (SI). It should be noted that the increase in the SI value was practically independent of the presence of arterial hypertension in the patient groups. No statistically significant relationship was found when analyzing the values of the reflection index (RI). When analyzing data from the reactive hyperemia test, we found a decrease in the increase in signal amplitude in a significant number of patients, which is a sign of endothelial dysfunction and is observed even in a group of patients without clinical and laboratory signs of kidney damage. However, along with this decrease in the index, a large number of patients have paradoxically high values, which may indicate an elevated basal level of nitric oxide.

Conclusion.

Increased aortic stiffness with the development of DN may be an early sign of macrovascular lesions even in patients without hypertension. The increase in post-occlusion signal amplitude in a group of patients without signs of kidney damage indicates the presence of endothelial dysfunction even in the preclinical stage of diabetic nephropathy. A paradoxically high increase in signal amplitude may indicate the presence of excessively high basal levels of nitric oxide, which is a marker of inflammation and a high risk factor for the development of angiopathy and fibrosis.

Key words: *endothelial dysfunction, nitric oxide, arterial wall stiffness, type 1 diabetes mellitus.*

Introduction

Currently, the prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) and its complications is increasing. Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is one of the main causes of the increase in the number of patients with chronic kidney disease requiring hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis [1]. DN is a leading cause of disability and death in patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM), representing a young population.

There are many clinical and experimental studies proving the involvement of endothelial disorders and the elastic properties of arteries in the development of vascular complications of diabetes [2-5]. In this regard, in studying the mechanisms of the development of DN, more attention is paid to the study of the arterial wall, including the assessment of the state of the endothelial layer and arterial stiffness. In this case, a special role is given to endothelial dysfunction, which is accompanied by a violation of the ability to produce nitric oxide, as well as an increase in the stiffness of elastic and muscular arteries. The increase in the stiffness of the arterial wall in patients with diabetes is associated with the process of glycation of the elastin fibers that make up its structure. With an increase in the stiffness of large elastic arteries, including the aorta, and muscular arteries, including the renal arteries, the ability to smooth out pressure pulsations in the renal microcirculation system decreases. Impaired ability of the arterial wall to attenuate pressure pulsations leads to impaired renal capillary function, which contributes to structural changes in the renal glomeruli and plays a key role in the onset and progression of renal pathology in patients with type 1 diabetes [6].

A clinically important task is to identify a group of patients with type 1 diabetes who are at high risk of developing and progressing angiopathies that require correction of disorders to prevent the development of vascular complications.

The state of endothelial vasoregulatory function is assessed using various methods. Invasive methods include chemical stimulation of endothelial muscarinic receptors with endothelium-stimulating drugs (acetylcholine, methacholine, substance P), as well as some direct vasodilators (nitroglycerin, sodium nitroprusside) injected into the artery and causing endothelium-independent vasodilation (measured using V-VOC).

However, noninvasive methods for assessing EDPVD, such as in response to sublingual nitroglycerin, have great advantages. One noninvasive method for assessing endothelium-dependent vasodilation (EDVD) is mechanical stimulation of the endothelium by increasing blood flow, which is assessed by changes in the diameter of the artery (usually the brachial artery) using high-resolution ultrasound.

This test is based on the occlusion test, which causes the development of reactive hyperemia in arteries located distal to the location of the occlusion cuff [7]. As a result of increased shear stress on the surface of the endothelial layer, nitric oxide is produced, which is accompanied by an increase in the diameter of the arteries and a decrease in their tone. A decrease in arterial tone leads to increased distensibility of the arterial wall, increasing the oscillations of the arterial diameter from diastolic to systolic positions. An increase in the range of oscillations of the arterial diameter is accompanied by an increase in the amplitude of the signal. The test result is assessed by an increase in the amplitude of the photoplethysmographic signal after occlusion. Angiophotoplethysmography is a highly effective method for assessing the state of the vascular bed with the possibility of studying EDVD. Our work

The aim of this study was to assess vascular wall stiffness and endothelial function in patients with type 1 diabetes at different stages of DN and without them.

Materials and methods

The study included 116 people. Of these, 93 were patients with type 1 diabetes and 23 were in the control group (healthy volunteers). The group of patients with type 1 diabetes included patients aged 18 to 40 years (45 men and 48 women), with a mean age of 28.13 ± 5.56 years, and a disease duration of more than 5 years. 38 of them had arterial hypertension. Exclusion criteria: terminal renal failure, dialysis treatment, the presence of severe concomitant pathology, systemic vascular diseases, obesity. All patients were treated in the hospital at the Research Center for Endocrinology in 2009-2011. The main criterion for forming groups of patients with type 1 diabetes was the presence of DN. Normoalbuminuria (NAU) was present in 47 (50.5%) patients, microalbuminuria (MAU) in 15 (16.2%), proteinuria (PU) in 14 (15%), and chronic renal failure (CRF) in 17 (18.3%). Diabetic retinopathy (DR) was observed in 68 individuals. 34 (50%) had nonproliferative DR, 10 (14.7%) had proliferative DR, and 24 (35.3%) had proliferative stage DR. Diabetic polyneuropathy was detected in 61 subjects examined, 23% of whom had diabetic foot syndrome. The control group consisted of 23 healthy individuals (18 women and 5 men), whose mean age was 25 ± 2.2 years.

The study included the assessment of pulse wave contour analysis using the Angioscan device and the reactive hyperemia test. Statistical data processing was performed using the SPSS 17.0 software package for Windows (SPSS Inc., 2008). Parameters were tested for normal distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The obtained data are presented as mean values (M) \pm standard deviation (SD). The significance of differences was assessed using non-parametric statistical methods: Mann-Whitney U-test for two independent samples. The significance of differences between groups for frequency indicators was assessed using the chi-square test. Statistically significant values were considered reliable at $p < 0.05$ for two-sided comparisons;

Informed consent was obtained from all patients before inclusion in the study.

Pulse wave contour analysis and reactive hyperemia test were performed in the morning hours, in a comfortable sitting position, in a quiet room, at a comfortable temperature of 20-22 ° C. Fatty, rich foods, smoking and coffee drinking were excluded before the study. During the test, the patient's arms were motionless, and the arms on which the sensors were installed were at heart level. The legs should not be crossed over each other, the bladder should be empty. Talking was not allowed during the test. If the test needs to be repeated, it can be performed 30 minutes after the first test. Before inflation, the occlusive cuff should allow a finger to pass freely through the gap between the cuff and the skin of the shoulder.

To perform the occlusion, a standard sphygmomanometer cuff was placed on the subject's shoulder and inflated to a pressure 50 mm Hg above the systolic pressure. Art. The duration of the occlusion was 5 minutes, after which the cuff pressure was quickly released, which led to a short-term increase in blood flow velocity in the brachial artery. The increase in blood flow velocity, in turn, led to an increase in shear stress on the surface of the endothelial layer. Endothelial cell mechanoreceptors help activate the synthesis of nitric oxide from L-arginine using the endothelial NO synthase enzyme. The synthesized nitric oxide acts on the smooth muscles of the arterial walls, causing a decrease in their tone and, therefore, increasing the amplitude of the signal. To record this effect, the signal was monitored for 90 seconds. The test result was assessed by an increase in the diameter of the brachial artery after occlusion.

The study protocol includes:

a representative volume pulse wave curve recorded from the working arm;

the maximum points of the direct and reflected waves on a given curve;

time analysis by determining the time between the direct and reflected wave;

Calculation of the stiffness index (SI), for which the height of the subject in meters is divided by the time between the direct and reflected waves in seconds. The stiffness index is measured in m/s , its value is related to the speed of propagation of the impulse wave. The value of SI is determined primarily by the stiffness of the aorta. In turn, the stiffness of the aorta depends on the age of the subject and his blood pressure (normal values are given in Table 1). In contrast to the variable systolic and diastolic pressures, the mean arterial pressure (MAP) is relatively constant and is calculated by the formula (B. Folkov, E. Neel, 1976): $MAP = P_{diast} + (P_{syst} - P_{diast})/3$;

amplitude analysis with calculation of the reflection index (RI), which indicates the tone of small resistive arteries. To calculate it, the amplitude of the reflected wave was divided by the amplitude of the direct wave, and the resulting number was multiplied by 100%. Normal RI is 50% or less, i.e. the amplitude of the reflected signal should not exceed half the amplitude of the direct wave;

Analysis of the occlusion test chart with calculation of the percentage increase in signal amplitude (PAS). Typically, a 1.5- to 2-fold increase in PAS is observed after occlusion when endothelial cells are able to produce nitric oxide.

Results

In the analysis, the aortic stiffness index was significantly higher in all groups of patients with DN compared with healthy subjects. However, when comparing patients with type 1 diabetes without DN with the control group, no significant differences were found in the SI index. It is worth noting that the increase in the SI value was practically independent of the presence of arterial hypertension in the patient groups.

When analyzing data from the reactive hyperemia test, we found a decrease in PAS in a significant number of patients, which is a sign of endothelial dysfunction and is observed even in a group of patients without clinical and laboratory signs of kidney damage. However, along with this decrease in the indicator, a large proportion of patients have paradoxically high values (more than 2 times)

It is worth noting that there is a strong positive correlation between DN and PAS variables ($r=0.99$, $p=0.001$). Furthermore, a decrease in PAS predominates in patients with NAU and in the MAU stage, while an increase in PAS predominates in patients with severe kidney damage.

When analyzing the values of the PAS indicator exceeding the target values, no statistically significant relationship was found with age and gender. As the duration of the disease increased, an increase in the frequency of detection of paradoxically high PAS values was noted.

Discussion

Many previous studies [8-10] have assessed endothelial function in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes (T2DM) and various comorbidities. In these studies, a decrease in PAS was noted as a predictor of the development and progression of vascular complications of diabetes mellitus when assessing EDVD in a test with reactive hyperemia. Our aim was to study the state of the endothelium in patients with type 1 diabetes, young, without vascular pathology (not associated with diabetes mellitus) and without additional risk factors for cardiovascular disease. A decrease in signal amplitude is a well-known sign of endothelial dysfunction: insufficient production of nitric oxide by endothelial cells due to their damage. We found confirmation of this fact in our work. However, in many patients with microvascular complications, along with a decrease in PAS, we observed its paradoxical increase (more than 2 times). And the more pronounced the complications, the more the increase in PAS prevailed over the decrease. We observed the highest values in patients with the most severe renal dysfunction, which may indicate an increase in blood NO levels in this category of patients.

Endothelial NO synthesis occurs as a result of the action of endothelial NO synthase (eNOS) and is directly dependent on the integrity of the endothelium. A decrease in NO production indicates damage to the endothelial layer, which leads to the development and progression of angiopathies. At the same time, it is of great interest that in response to the action of many pathogenic stimuli, anti-inflammatory factors, on the contrary, excessive secretion of NO has been detected, which is associated with the action of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS). This stimulates the release of large amounts of nitric oxide for many hours and days, increasing the level of NO several times [11]. Hyperproduction of NO, in turn, has a cytotoxic and cytostatic effect, leading to excessive vasodilation and tissue damage. As shown in the work of LDK Buttery et al., increased expression of iNOS is also found in atherosclerotic vascular lesions. [12].

With the development of diabetic microangiopathies, endothelial cells, as a result of their developing dysfunction, practically do not produce NO, platelets and mononuclear cells regulate vascular tone, producing NO. The synthesis of NO by platelets increases with their aggregation. One of the mechanisms of development and progression of diabetic angiopathy may be an increase in the functional activity of blood cells.

Many previous studies confirm that patients with type 1 diabetes with microvascular complications have increased NO production compared to healthy individuals and patients without microangiopathy [13].

There is reason to believe that in diabetes mellitus and in hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia, oxidative stress, and cytokine disorders, the system regulating NO production undergoes complex changes. In the early stages of vascular damage, endothelial dysfunction develops, followed by a decrease in endothelial NO production. Under such conditions, iNOS expression is a compensatory mechanism to replenish the NO pool. Under such conditions, high levels of NO in patients with angiopathy can counteract the effects of pathogenic factors such as thromboxane and endothelin-1, the production of which is significantly increased in patients with diabetic angiopathy [14]. However, with prolonged exposure, hyperproduction of NO begins to have a detrimental effect on tissues, leading to the predominance of vasoconstriction and the development of diabetic angiopathies [2].

Thus, in the younger group of patients with type 1 diabetes, who are at high risk of developing angiopathies, a sharp increase in PAS may occur in the presence of an increase in basal levels of NO in the blood during a test with reactive hyperemia. In elderly patients, this effect may be compensated by the presence of atherosclerotic changes in the blood vessels.

Conclusion

1. With the development of DN, an increase in the SI index, even in the absence of signs of arterial hypertension, may be an early sign of damage to large vessels (aorta).
2. The decrease in PAS in the group of patients without signs of kidney damage indicates the presence of endothelial dysfunction even in the preclinical stage of DN.
3. Paradoxically, a high PAS may indicate the presence of excessively high basal levels of nitric oxide, which is a marker of inflammation and a high risk factor for the development of angiopathy and fibrosis.

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